

Spectrophotometric estimation of celecoxib in bulk and its pharmaceutical formulation

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Abstract : A new simple, precise, sensitive, highly specific and economical ultraviolet spectrophotometric method for the determination of celecoxib in bulk and its pharmaceutical formulation (dispersible tablets and capsules) has been developed. The absorbance maxima of celecoxib in a mixture of methanol and 0.01 *N* sodium hydroxide (1 : 1 v/v) were determined at 253.1 nm. Beer's law is obeyed over concentration range of 8–22 µg/ml with correlation coefficient $r > 0.999$. The results have been validated statistically and by recovery studies.

Keywords : Spectrophotometry, celecoxib, sodium hydroxide, methanol, correlation coefficient.

Introduction

Celecoxib, 4-[5-(4-methylphenyl)-3-(trifluoromethyl)-1*H*-pyrazol-1-yl]benzenesulfonamide a non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID), is a highly selective COX-2 inhibitor and is approximately 7.6 times more selective towards COX-2 inhibition than COX-1 with minimal gastrointestinal adverse drug reactions. Pharmacological studies have shown that celecoxib is effective in the treatment of osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, acute pain, painful menstruation and menstrual symptoms¹. Recent clinical trials performed proved its efficacy in the treatment of cervical dysplasia², chemoprevention of colorectal cancer³ and prostate cancer⁴.

Several analytical methods, such as UV spectrophotometry^{5,6} high performance liquid chromatography^{7–12}, of celecoxib in bulk and pharmaceutical formulation have been reported. Various solvents employed for different methods, suffer from disadvantages like lack of accuracy, stability, sensitivity and specificity.

Hence it is thought worthwhile to develop a simple and precise spectrophotometric method using methanol and 0.01 *N* sodium hydroxide in the ratio 1 : 1 v/v as a solvent for the estimation of celecoxib in bulk and its pharmaceutical formulation.

Results and discussion

The present study was carried out to develop a simple, accurate and sensitive UV spectrophotometric method for the determination of celecoxib in tablets and capsules. In the present investigation, methanol and 0.01 *N* sodium hydroxide in the ratio 1 : 1 v/v was found to be a better solvent. The optical characteristics are : Beer's law limit (8–22 µg/ml), absorbance maxima (253.1 nm), molar absorptivity (567.18 L M⁻¹ cm⁻¹), Sandell's sensitivity (0.017633 µg cm⁻¹/0.001 absorbance unit), correlation coefficient ($r = 0.999$), slope ($m = 0.055$) and intercept ($c = 0.0081$), % relative standard deviation (0.163), % range of error was found to be 0.102 and 0.013 at 0.05 and 0.01 confidence limit respectively. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity shows that the method is sensitive. Limit of detection (LOD) and limit of confidence (LOQ) were 0.0783 and 0.2612 µg/ml respectively. The method was found to be precise as percentage relative standard deviation for intra-day and inter-day precision were 0.182 and 0.185 respectively (Table 3). Accuracy of the method was calculated by percentage mean recovery ($n = 3$). The recoveries studies were carried out by the addition of standard analyte to the preanalyzed sample. The concentrations of standard spiked to both the sample were 8 to 12 µg/ml of celecoxib. The mean per-

Note

Table 1. Analysis result of formulations I and II

Formulation	Labelled amount of celecoxib (mg)	Amount obtained (mg) ^a	% of drug present	% RSD
Celact (tablet)	200	198.26 ± 0.636	99.13	0.642
Zyclal (capsule)	200	196.61 ± 0.770	98.30	0.785

^aEach value is average of three determinations ± standard deviation

Table 2. Recovery data of celecoxib tablet and capsule by the proposed method

Sample ID	Concentration of pure drug (µg/ml)	Concentration of tablet formulation (µg/ml)	% Recovery of pure drug	Statistical analysis
Tablet :				
T : 80%	8	10	99.88	Mean 99.89 S D. 0.5039 % RSD 0.5044
T : 100%	10	10	99.54	Mean 99.20 S D 0.5903 % RSD 0.5951
T : 120%	12	10	100.39	Mean 100.39 S.D. 0.1893 % RSD 0.1886
Capsule :				
C : 80%	8	10	100.09	Mean 100.67 S.D. 0.2423 % RSD 0.2407
C : 100%	10	10	99.98	Mean 100.097 S D. 0.5896 % RSD 0.589
C : 120%	12	10	99.40	Mean 99.39 S D 0.1893 % RSD 0.186

Table 3. Results of precision studies

Amount taken (µg/ml)	Inter-day		Intra-day	
	Amount found (µg/ml)	% RSD	Amount found (µg/ml)	% RSD
14	13.97	0.171	13.95	0.149
14	13.98		13.90	
14	13.93		13.92	
16	15.87	0.131	15.97	0.232
16	15.90		15.92	
16	15.85		15.88	
18	17.91	0.254	17.96	0.164
18	17.87		17.89	
18	17.98		17.91	

centage recovery was found to be 99.83 for tablets (Celact) and 100.05 for capsules (Zycel). Low values of percentage relative standard deviation (0.136 and 0.1302) observed in the ruggedness studies (16 µg/ml) of the proposed method. The assay values for the marketed formulations I and II were found to be within the limit as listed in Table 1.

The proposed method was found to be simple, precise, accurate and sensitive. High percentage recovery showed that the method was free from interference of excipients used in the formulation. Values of LOD and LOQ showed that the proposed method was sensitive enough to analyze the drug in bulk as well as in its pharmaceutical formulation. Hence the proposed method is suitable for routine analysis in quality-control laboratories.

Experimental

Material and methods :

A Systronic 2210 double beam UV/Vis spectrophotometer with 10 mm matched quartz cells was used in the present study. The chemicals used were of analytical grade. Celecoxib tablets, Celact (Sun Pharmaceutical Industries Ltd., Mumbai) and capsules, Zycel (Zydus Cadila, Mumbai) were procured from local market. Celecoxib (analyzed sample) as provided by Zydus Cadila Laboratories (Ahmedabad, India) was used as such without further purification.

A solution of Celecoxib was prepared by dissolving 50 mg of standard celecoxib in a 50 ml mixture of methanol and 0.01 N sodium hydroxide (1 : 1 v/v) and suitably diluted to get a working standard solution of 1000 µg/ml. Aliquots (8, 1, 1.2....2.2 ml) of working standard solution were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks to obtain final drug concentration of 8 to 22 µg/ml. Linearity relationship was observed in the range 8 to 22 µg/ml against a reagent blank as reference at 253.1 nm.

Average weight of twenty tablets and capsules were determined, then finely powdered (separately for each of the two formulations tested). The powdered amount equivalent to 200 mg (accurately weighed) was extracted with 100 ml of mixture methanol and 0.01 N sodium hydroxide (1 : 1 v/v) for 45 min. The suspension was filtered. The filtrate was diluted to 200 ml with the same solvent.

A 5 ml portion of this solution was diluted to 50 ml and then further diluted to obtain a concentration of 12 µg/ml, 14 µg/ml and 16 µg/ml of celecoxib respectively. The absorbances of these solutions were determined at 253.1 nm against a reagent blank. The amount of celecoxib determined in both the sample is presented in Table 1.

The repeatability of the method was established by carrying out ($n = 8$) the analysis of analyte (16 µg/ml) using the proposed method. The mean and standard deviation values of repeatability result are 0.896 and 0.00146 respectively. The low value of percentage relative standard deviation (0.163) showed that the method is precise.

The accuracy of the method was evaluated by calculating the recovery of celecoxib by standard addition method at concentration of 80%, 100% and 120% of the target level in tablets and capsules. The results are presented in Table 2.

The precision of the method was demonstrated by inter-day and intra-day variation studies using three different concentrations of drug. In intra-day studies, drug was analyzed on the same day while inter-day precision was determined by analyzing drug for three days over a period of one week and results are presented in Table 3. Ruggedness of the proposed method was determined at 16 µg/ml on different instruments by different analyst under similar environment.

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